

The Relationship Between Common Sense and Thinking: Keeping with the Event in Education

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Introduction

In this article, I investigate the relationship between common sense and thinking. Two prominent philosophers of our Western tradition that have problematized the notions of common sense and thinking from different yet similar perspectives are Gilles Deleuze and Hannah Arendt. Common sense and thinking are both to be understood in juxtaposition to the notion of the *event*. The event is something that happens to us from the outside, while at the same time it is captured in our linguistic expressions, yet not contained within them.

The article is organized as follows. The first section accounts for the philosophy of Gilles Deleuze and his views on thinking, sense and the event. Although his concepts are manifold and connect with one another in multiple ways, I have restricted myself to keeping with the concepts noted above. Additional concepts such as virtual intensities will be embedded in my discussion as an element of the aforementioned concepts and not as free-standing ones (although none of his concepts are free-standing). Following that, I account for Hannah Arendt's philosophy based on my reading of *The Human Condition* and *The Life of the Mind*, by addressing her notions of thinking, judging and common sense. In the third section, I show how Deleuze and Arendt can be read through one another by directing my attention to their respective takes on common sense. I conclude my paper with a discussion of how common sense and thinking, read through Deleuze and Arendt, have implications for education.

Images of Thinking

In *Difference and Repetition* (2014), we come across Deleuze's "image of thought." Images of thought are the philosophical presuppositions that have permeated Western philosophical thinking dating back to Plato. The images of thought ground thinking and steer it in a certain direction in that presuppositions are not called into question. For instance, the Cartesian image of thought captured by the *cogito* presupposes "that everybody knows what it means to think" (Deleuze, 2014). It presupposes a subject *detached* from the world, the object, which the subject can strive to get to know (Colebrook, 2001).

This Cartesian image, Deleuze explains, contains three levels: a naturally upright thought, an in-principle natural common sense, and a transcendental model of recognition (2014, p. 177). These assumptions, Deleuze claims, are pre-philosophical since they constitute the inner condition for thinking without being subjected to scrutiny themselves. We are not actually thinking with this image in place; we are merely recognizing. The "I think" is presupposed to be the unifier of all

our faculties, and the *cogito* becomes the philosophical concept of common sense. For Deleuze, true thought is “primarily trespass and violence, the enemy, and nothing presupposes philosophy: everything begins with misosophy” (2014, p. 183). What forces us to think is an object of an encounter, not recognition, and its primary characteristic is that it can only be *sensed*. From the perspective of recognition, it is imperceptible.

What Deleuze seeks to liberate is “pure difference.” Pure difference is difference *in itself* and cannot as such be reduced to the separative nature of habitual thought and recognition in which difference gains its tenor through comparison. For instance, when we say, “Lars is different from Laila,” we merely erect a fence between them, routinely grafted on current cultural understandings, for example gender, in which the difference of Lars is completely dependent on the identity of Laila. Within common-sense understanding, with rigid and solidified analytical categories (for instance man/woman), we lose the two-fold sense of pure difference: firstly, difference as *transfiguration*; and secondly, difference as *immanent within the actual* (Bogue, 2004).

The Immanent Event

Deleuze draws a line between morality and ethics. Morality, Deleuze claims, is rooted in a representational image of thought (Spangenberg, 2009, p. 90). This representational image presupposes who we are and what we ought to do, rather than what we have the potential to become. What hinders us from exceeding who we are, and becoming something different, is identity and habitual thinking. Deleuze holds the view that when we identify, we represent, and when we represent, we remove ourselves from the potentiality of becoming imperceptible. Identity in representation prevents us from experiencing the virtual intensities of pure difference. To enable thinking, and to counteract recognition, Deleuze introduces his notion of Ideas with a capital ‘I’ to distinguish his understanding of Ideas from our common usage of ideas as contained in our minds (Spangenberg, 2009, p. 94). Ideas and problems constitute the transcendental conditions for thought for Deleuze. In the *Logic of Sense* (2015), sense is understood as identical with the event (Deleuze, 1990). Since Ideas reside in the virtual realm, they can only be sensed and not contained within a representational scheme. For Deleuze, sensations and virtual intensities “are the virtual but necessary conditions for the occurrence of significant events” (Spangenberg, 2009, p. 94). Events, Deleuze continues, are incorporeal entities that are expressed through language yet subsist beyond their manifestation. Concepts, in that they are created as a response (not a solution) to particular problems, are an example of events.

Thus, what is expressed in a proposition, the sense/event, is distinguished from the bodies it denotes. In this way, the virtual and the actual are interconnected yet belong to different orders. Common sense for Deleuze is always representational and hence dogmatic and moral. We need to be ethically attuned to the event to actualize pure thought. In Spangenberg’s words, “Deleuze conceives of ethics as an event and as inextricably linked with the sole aim of philosophy: to become imperceptible or, as Deleuze would also say, to become worthy of the event” (2009, p. 90). And how do we do that?

To be worthy of the event, we need to extract the virtual event from a state of affairs. This move Deleuze calls a “counter-actualization.” For example, say one has an unusual experience while reading a novel. The particular novel elicits new and uncommon sensations in the reader. Perhaps

the narrator in the story presents a perceptual field that seems completely alien to the reader. This experience is first and foremost *sensed* rather than comprehended, Deleuze would claim, in that the encounter with this new way of perceiving is not eligible for representation and identification: the sensation, encounter, forces us to think *involuntarily*. This encounter with something new and different ignites an idea constitutive of a problem that actualizes thinking in that we are forced to explicate something of which there exists no pre-given representation. In other words, we experience difference as transfiguration and immanent within the actual. Now, a counter-actualization would be to immerse oneself in that creative flow unleashed by the new encounter, to be transformed, and bring that process of transformation into new situations.

The Creation of Concepts

In *What is Philosophy?* (2014), Deleuze, and Guattari present their view on immanence, or more precisely “the plane of immanence.” Philosophy, they contend, is constructivism with the purpose of creating concepts and laying out a plane of immanence. The plane is presupposed in that concepts refer to a non-conceptual understanding. If philosophy involves the creation of concepts, then the plane is the ground for the creation itself. However, this does not mean that the pre-philosophical is outside of philosophy or that it precedes it, although it is pre-supposed by philosophy:

Philosophy is at once concept creation and instituting of the plane. The concept is the beginning of philosophy, but the plane is its instituting. The plane is clearly not a program, design, end, or means: it is a plane of immanence that constitutes the absolute ground of philosophy, its earth or deterritorialization, the foundation on which it creates its concepts. Both the creation of concepts and the instituting of the plane are required, like two wings or fins. (p. 41)

The plane of immanence *is* the image of thought: “The plane of immanence is not a concept that is or can be thought but rather the image of thought, the image thought gives itself of what it means to think, to make use of thought, to find one’s bearings in thought” (p. 41). Important to note is that the plane of immanence is not a concept in itself since a concept is always a response to a problem and hence cannot constitute a foundation. The image of thought is thus no longer dogmatic, since it is now a movable plane, not a re-presentation. With the plane of immanence, Deleuze and Guattari understand an infinite yet absolute horizon from which thinking is given consistency:

Concepts are concrete assemblages, like the configurations of a machine, but the plane is the abstract machine of which these assemblages are the working parts. Concepts are events, but the plane is the horizon of events, the reservoir or reserve of purely conceptual events: not the relative horizon that functions as a limit, which changes with an observer and encloses observable states of affairs, but the absolute horizon, independent of any observer, which makes the event as concept independent of a visible state of affairs in which it is brought about. (Guattari and Deleuze, 2014, p. 36)

The image of thought, Deleuze and Guattari explain, “implies a strict division between fact and *right*.” Thus, historical facts or facts pertaining to the function of the brain are contingent and must therefore be separated from thought as such: “The image of thought retains only what thought can claim by right. Thought demands ‘only’ movement that can be carried to infinity. What thought claims by right, what it selects, is infinite movement or the movement of the infinite. It is this that constitutes the image of thought” (2014, p. 37). Immanence, in the words of Claire Colebrook, is “not the ground or foundation of life; the plane of immanence is the thought of that which produces any ground” (2001, p. 77).

With this understanding of philosophy in place, we are able to move beyond the grip of representation and measure philosophy in terms of effectivity. The creation of concepts underwrites the actualization of virtual relations and as a corollary establishes an interconnection between the virtual and the actual, not due to concepts’ ability to refer, but to concepts’ ability to express sense. As we have seen, sense belongs to the virtual realm, but is also always part of the actual world. Reality is never fully grasped unless both virtual intensities and actual states of affairs are accounted for (Spangenberg, 2009).

The Active Life

We now turn to Hannah Arendt. In *The Human Condition*, Arendt discusses three activities that underpin human life: labor, work and action. Each activity corresponds to a basic human condition. The basic condition for labor is life itself. We need to labor to provide ourselves with the necessities of food and shelter. The corresponding condition for work is worldliness. Through work humans create a shared world in the form of communities, objects and culture. Action corresponds to the basic condition of plurality. Action can only take place in the presence of other people. All three activities and their corresponding conditions are underpinned by the conditions for life: natality and mortality. Natality signifies a new beginning—we are born into this world as newcomers, which always implies that new actions are initiated and that the consequences reach beyond our grasp and control. In action and speech, we disclose not just the action in itself but *who* we are. Unlike labor and work, action can never be tamed nor performed in a way in which the individual loses its *who*.

Judgment

Arendt’s notion of judgment is based on Kant’s notion of aesthetic judgment and *sensus communis*, respectively. An aesthetic judgment can be deductive or reflective; the former moves from the general to the particular and the latter moves from the particular to the general. For Kant, judgment is the ability to think the particular as subsumed under a universal. Through the particular we can ascend to the generality of a certain concept; for instance, stumbling upon a beautiful sculpture might give one an understanding of what beauty is. It is only through the particular that the universal can arise. In the particular, we can see the universal at the same time as the particular retains its particularity. For Arendt, it is the spectators that are in a position to judge events impartially. To do this, they make use of two faculties: imagination and common sense. Imagination means that we represent for our mind events that have already taken place; this representation thus establishes a distance from which we can make a disinterested judgment. When this distance has been established, we can view the representations from multiple perspectives;

that is, we are able to enact representative thinking. The other faculty that spectators have to make use of is common sense or *sensus communis*, since without it, spectators would not be able to transcend their subjective position of judging. Hence, judgments need to be communicable intersubjectively with other members of the same community. Arendt again draws on Kant and uses the notion of an “enlarged mentality” in order to show how the spectator’s verdict, although impartial, still relies on the views of others (1981, p. 94). A spectator is thus withdrawn from the scene of action to be able to understand the spectacle.

Two Types of Common Sense

Israeli philosopher Itay Snir points out that “The most radical aspect of Arendt’s conception of common sense” (2020, p. 73) is that it does not exist automatically in a society: it has to be created and maintained continuously. We judge within a common sense, but we also intervene and reconstruct common sense through our judging actions. Common-sense understanding and reasoning is not a static feature of the world; rather, it is brought forward by people inhabiting a specific place in which common sense is always up for grabs. The corresponding worldly property of our sixth sense, common sense, is realness:

In a world of appearances, filled with error and semblance, reality is guaranteed by this three-fold commonness: the five senses, utterly different from each other, have the same object in common, members of the same species have the context in common that endows every single object with its particular meaning; and all other sense-endowed beings, though perceiving this object from utterly different perspectives, agree on its identity. Out of this threefold commonness arises the *sensation* of reality. (Arendt, 1981, p. 50)

Although our sixth sense is not strictly speaking a sense on par with our five senses, since its worldly property cannot be perceived, it brings about a sensation of realness, a thereness, which always takes place in a specific context of appearances (1981, p. 51). We can identify two types of common sense herein: i) common sense as imagination, representation and judgment (an enlarged mentality); ii) common sense as a sixth sense which brings about the sensation of realness, anchored in the functions and worldly properties of our five general senses. Both of these understandings of common sense are targets for Deleuze’s criticism, as we saw above.

Thinking as Afterthought and the Creation of Meaning

Thinking for Arendt is the silent dialogue between me and myself. Thinking demands a withdrawal from everyday practice, from the world of appearances, in that the thinking process, although prompted by everyday experience, needs to de-sense that which has appeared in order for the thinking process to create “thought-things.” Thus, common sense, our sensation of realness, is suspended in the act of thinking (1981, p. 52).

Thinking is always an afterthought; it comes *after the event*. The afterthought can suddenly hit us, creep up on us, as it were, or be voluntarily recalled and mulled over. In the search for meaning, which the afterthought gives rise to, we do not simply replay events that have taken place, but rather pick them apart and move beyond them as part of the search for meaning. That is, in thinking

we recall events *and* create meaning for further thought; thought always goes further (Arendt, 1981). Thus, within the thinking process that Arendt discusses, we can see similarities with Deleuze's actual-virtual dimensions of thinking and reality, in that thinking and the creation of meaning are never conditioned by a foreseeable terminus.

When we think, we are in solitude, and we present for our minds episodes that have already taken place. In this re-presentation we rely on both memory and imagination. Note that although the contingency of everyday appearances is of a different order than the thinking process itself, the former gives rise to the latter. The activity of thinking has no goal that lies outside of itself; rather, the process of thinking in itself is the aim. Moreover, when the thinking process comes to an end, we find ourselves back in the everyday world of appearances in which doing, and not thinking, takes place. When we are in the midst of everyday practice, for instance when we are engaged in a lively discussion with friends, we are not thinking, although we obviously make use of our cognitive abilities, since we are not in solitude, which is the prerequisite of having an inner dialogue between me and myself.

Thinking, Knowledge and Judging

Arendt differentiates thinking from knowing. Knowing is concerned with truth, whereas thinking is concerned with meaning. Thinking concerns itself with unanswerable questions, and there is no finality to the process of thinking in the form of a tangible object, which is the success of knowledge. Through thinking, we seek to understand the meaning of events in which the taxonomy of true and false has no abode. However, this does not mean that meaning and truth are fully separate. Thinking arises from knowledge, and knowledge would be impossible to obtain without thinking. Yet while related, they are of different orders, as we have seen.

For Arendt, the faculty of judging is interrelated with the faculty of thinking in that thinking has a liberating effect on the judging spectator who realizes thinking in the public realm, in which thinking itself can never take place. Judging thus makes thinking manifest, a "thinking" that is not knowledge but the ability to tell right from wrong, beautiful from ugly. The difference between thinking and judging is that judging takes place in the world of appearances, whereas thinking demands a withdrawal from that very same world. However, judging is the ability both to tell right from wrong and to draw on our imagination in order to enact representative thinking. Thus, we are thinking, but in the form of a spectator in whom the inner dialogue between me and myself is not actualized. The withdrawal demanded by the spectator is one from action rather than one from the world of appearances. The withdrawal is necessary in order to see the whole. But it does not demand solitude. On the contrary, the spectator's verdict depends on the views of others, an "enlarged mentality," as Arendt explained in her lectures on Kant. Judging, like thinking, takes place in isolation, in the moment when imagination is used to represent the perspective of other people. The withdrawal of judgment, unlike thinking, is still located within the world of appearances. However, the precondition for representative thinking is interaction with other people in a shared world in which common sense is created.

Thinking, as we have seen, does not yield tangible rules of conduct or a stable foundation for acting morally. What it does yield is a critical examination of present norms, conventions and political systems that are contingent and thus always open for discussion and change. Conscience is a

byproduct of thinking that stems from the inner dialogue between me and myself. The ground for telling right from wrong is “subjective in two senses. First, what I can bear to have done without losing my internal harmony might change from one individual to another, or depend on historical and political circumstances. Second, moral judgments turn on the question of with whom I wish to be, namely on something resembling concrete human interaction, not on abstract standards and rules that allow for Platonic objectivity” (Snir, 2020, p. 64). Although thinking deals with invisibles while judgment deals with particulars, they are interconnected, as we have seen, in that thinking is actualized in judgment, when we tell right from wrong, but without instating universal rules of conduct.

Thus, thinking dissolves firm categories and prepares the activity of judging particulars without using universals as guideposts. In other words, judgment is our public manifestation of thinking critically. Thinking thus gives options for actions. So judgment is our outer manifestation of thought; but how do we communicate our thinking to other people? Arendt, again following Kant, proposes metaphors as mediators for thinking. Through metaphorical language, we can make manifest the *experience of thinking* and not the thinking process itself, since it demands solitude. The experience of thinking is transferred in speech through metaphorical language. In Arendt’s words,

Analogies, metaphors, and emblems are the threads by which the mind holds on to the world even when, absentmindedly, it has lost direct contact with it, and they guarantee the unity of human experience. Moreover, in the thinking process itself they serve as models to give us our bearings lest we stagger blindly among experiences that our bodily senses with their relative certainty of knowledge cannot guide us through. The simple fact that our mind is able to find such analogies, that the world of appearances reminds us of things non-apparent, may be seen as a kind of “proof” that mind and body, thinking and sense experience, the invisible and the visible, belong together, are “made” for each other, as it were. (1981, p. 109)

Metaphors bring together the invisible and the visible. The abyss between the two modes is thus bridged. The ongoing process of thinking, Arendt says, is like “Penelope’s web; it undoes every morning what it has finished the night before” (1981, p. 88). But the “only possible” metaphor for thinking itself, Arendt states, “is the sensation of being alive” (1981, p. 123). A potential danger with all thinking, Arendt claims, is to confuse thinking with a withdrawal from the world of human affairs. We have seen that thinking indeed demands solitude; however, solitude is not to be confused with loneliness. Thinking is, furthermore, always tied to action, and action always takes place amid fellow individuals. This is why Arendt draws on Socrates in fleshing out the life of the mind, in that he operated in the *polis* and tried to draw out truth from opinions (*doxa*). That is, he did not try to impose philosophical truths upon opinions, but rather engaged in dialogue, trying to make *doxa* more truthful.

So, thinking is both something that takes place in solitude, in the inner dialogue between me and myself, and an outer manifestation in judgment and action. In action, we are in the world of appearances, and when acting, we are judged by spectators who make use of imagination and common sense to evaluate the actions on display. Both action and judgment are underpinned by plurality.

Arendt and Deleuze Making (Common) Sense

Imagination is used by both Arendt and Deleuze to transcend our own narrow subject and our human point of view as a way of unleashing thinking from firm banisters. The philosophy of common sense that Deleuze criticizes is one in which sense is defined as the condition of truth, whereas Arendt defines common sense as a political faculty in which opinions are formed. Within the philosophy of Arendt, thinking, judgment and action are ontologically rooted in natality and plurality. The initiation of something new, conditioned by the fact that we are born into a world populated by other acting subjects, shapes our course of action from the viewpoint of the actor, and our ability to judge from the standpoint of the spectator. We are free to act and judge in the sense that we are unique and able to set something in motion. However, this freedom is hinged on the unexpectedness of action and does not stem from an isolated will. The subject never acts alone; its uniqueness and ability to act and judge is dependent on other people, that is, on plurality. Through the faculty of imagination, we are able to represent other people's viewpoints from the standpoint of our subjective selves. This imagination is preconditioned by the actual involvement and interaction with other people. Thus, Arendt is not assuming an established image of thought before representative thinking is enacted.

The notion of common sense that Deleuze is attacking is one in which all our faculties are understood to work together to recognize, identify and subsume. This is how common sense is reproduced; we merely recognize, and in recognizing, we are not thinking, since we are under the chairmanship of the dogmatic image of thought. Thinking, for Deleuze, is preceded by a shocking encounter with an object that forces us to think and on which our senses no longer work jointly to recognize; from the view of perception, what we encounter is imperceptible.

Arendt, like Deleuze, draws on Kant's understanding of common sense, which, as we have seen, moves beyond the mere harmonizing exercise of our five senses. Whilst Deleuze settles with the understanding of common sense as recognition and doxa, Arendt pushes the envelope further in positing a common sense that is always in flux, and not a natural part of a society; it is always being created, maintained, eradicated. Moreover, common sense for Arendt is pre-conditioned by the interaction with others, but not in a fashion that leads to expressions, such as "everybody knows what it means to think." On the contrary, Arendt's *sensus communis* thrives on plurality and difference, on the cultivation of different perspectives and standpoints. Thinking, strictly speaking, is not taking place in common sense for Arendt, just as for Deleuze. However, thinking, for Arendt, must always return to doxa to make sense, and to being part and parcel of our world of appearances. Through this move, Arendt inserts an element of thinking also within doxa—not the pure activity which demands solitude, but one instantiated in the spectator and the actor. From within common sense, thinking and action can thus emerge for Arendt, which for Deleuze suggests something close to an abomination in that the very "thinking" would be circumscribed by the dogmatic image of thought *which thinking contends to transcend*. However, that Deleuzian understanding becomes circumscribed itself, I claim, when plurality and difference are purged from the notion at the outset. His particular understanding of commonsensical reasoning as solely transmitted through recognition is a definition of common sense that Arendt seeks to transcend, but without throwing the baby out with the bathwater. When Arendt and Socrates roam the streets of the polis, they discover that *not* everybody knows what it means to think, and that it is *not* a natural capacity. A possible reply to my claim that Deleuze's conception of common sense

becomes circumscribed itself would be that common sense, in that it is representational and moral, is by necessity disconnected from virtual intensities and becomings. In line with this objection is the objection that Arendt's understanding of common sense, and of thinking and judging, is hinged on a presupposed subject that initiates independent action in this world. I believe that this tension is more apparent than real in that Deleuze's point of departure is the immanent difference of virtual events that are interconnected with actual states of affairs, whereas Arendt's point of departure is the acting and thinking subject contained within actual states of affairs. These two presuppositions are seemingly at odds with one another, but only if we close ourselves off to the virtual relationship between them. For instance, Deleuze claims that to stay close to the event, we have to enact counter-actualizations in the actual world. Arendt's judging spectator who says "no" to business as usual is, I claim, an example of a counter-actualization. Furthermore, Deleuze's notion of virtual intensities expands Arendt's notion of common sense and shows how we could transcend doxa with our faculty of thinking that, as a consequence, moves beyond a traditional or stale understanding of representational thinking. Thus, the Arendtian standpoint of another person need not solely be perceived as different *from* mine; it is different *in itself*.

With Arendt's notions of common sense and judgment, Deleuze's understanding of the interconnection between virtual intensities and actual states of affairs can be expanded upon through understanding Arendt's subject as anchored in a common world yet endowed with a faculty of thinking (and judgment) that never comes to a halt or relies upon logical principles.

Implications for Education

Education, for both Arendt and Deleuze, needs to move beyond the mere transmission of knowledge. In *Proust and Signs* (2000), Deleuze spells out an apprenticeship that the protagonist of Proust's *In Search of Lost Time* is undergoing. *The search*, for Deleuze, is not oriented towards the past but towards the future. Along the way, the protagonist learns that objects emitting signs do not contain the secret of the sign, and neither does the subjective interpreter. However, it is through the engagement with other people that the protagonist of the search comes to understand the process of explicating signs and rids himself of the illusions of pure objectivity and pure subjective interpretive associations. He comes to learn that essences, or what Deleuze deems differences, are internal in both objects and subjects alike, and that the signs being emitted need to be explicated rather than represented; we need to unfold that which the sign enfolds. We can read this approach through Arendt's understanding of the representation of other people's viewpoints from the viewpoint of oneself: *I think from where I stand, imagining that it could be different—the world as much as my outlook*.

Arendt's plurality and unicity bring about unexpected encounters, events, that give rise to thought that goes further than the identification of the emitted sign, that is the person/situation we come across, and looks for meaning and difference that demand explication rather than simple representation. However, a precondition for learning, or apprenticeship, for Arendt is to get to know the old world. Children must be taught our collective accumulated body of knowledge, customs and common sense to properly immerse themselves therein *and* to subsequently change it. In this regard, education must be conservative. Important to note is that the task of familiarizing youngsters with the old world for Arendt is not equivalent to inculcation, but, rather, to assuming responsibility for a future to come. Thus, the responsibility to acquaint the youngsters with the

old world stipulates more than the mere transmission of knowledge.

Deleuze would claim that however necessary, this is not education for thinking, but only for recognition. However, without the first step of recognition, we would be completely unmoored from the world and unable to cultivate thinking and open ourselves up to rare encounters and events. Of course, what Deleuze cautions against is the danger and inertia of *remaining* within the confines of common sense (and confusing structure of thought for thinking), not our colloquial usage of it. What we can learn from Arendt is that representation and explication must not be oppositional. When we represent, imagining a different viewpoint, we are in a position to judge things differently, counter to common sense, which in itself bears the power of changing common sense. Our judging faculty bears the promise of creation, and creation is always an event. For Arendt, common sense contains not only uncontested mundane knowledge from which we derive temporary “truths” and permissible conduct, but a sensation of realness that functions as an arena for action. When we act, we act as a response to the actions of others, and these others can readily be expanded to encompass signs, mental and physical objects, technology, natural phenomena and so forth, and remain consistent with Arendt’s philosophy at large.

Within a Deleuzian creative process, there is an Idea that is constitutive of problems. Common sense is for Arendt created rather than discovered. In representative thinking, we tackle head-on the problem of natality, the new beginning inherent in all actions unfolding from a specific point of view. Always different, always fleeting. Thinking in terms of creating concepts, in terms of withdrawal from the world of appearances and in terms of representative thinking, are all on par with being “worthy of the event,” in that sense resides in the problem itself. It is not about finding proper solutions to well-defined problems, but to continue thinking and expressing that sense/event through action and speech.

In education, then, Arendt’s and Deleuze’s common sense can join forces and point towards the cultivation of thinking: firstly, through getting to know the old world, and secondly, by creating a new one. Snir (2020) proposes that the inner dialogue between me and myself, a withdrawal from the world of appearances, is complemented with the faculty of judgment that thinking in solitude liberates. In an educational context, this can be formed as giving space for students to contemplate and engage with their peers through dialogue that opens up the possibility for actualizing representative thinking. A common sense is then both established and challenged in concert, with no pre-given goal as to where to arrive.

So, what can we learn from Arendt and Deleuze? From Arendt, we learn about a continuous inner dialogue from which public judgment can be cultivated. From Deleuze, we learn about the explicating process of interpreting signs from which sense and pure difference can be derived, paired with the creation of concepts.

A cultivation of judgment from thinking, and an open-ended examining of pre-suppositions (very much similar to getting to know the old world), can be merged, I claim, in that both steer us to move beyond business as usual, not for the sake of moving beyond—it is not the end-goal—but for the sake of creating a better world in which movement of thought can be actualized. Thus, for both Arendt and Deleuze, the main question is not what we can know *but what we can become*.

Conclusion

In this paper, I inquired into the concepts of common sense, thinking and the event through engaging with the philosophies of Hannah Arendt and Gilles Deleuze. I showed that common sense can be understood as both an intersubjective faculty in which opinions are formed and a representative thought-scheme that imprisons thought through actualizing recognition and identification rather than creative thinking. However, these two aspects are both important to keep in mind while examining the origin of common sense *and* thinking. When we realize that common sense imposes a thought-regime in which recognition is taken as an in-principle transcendental faculty of human perception, then we can more easily catch a sight of creative thought, thinking, as a process that momentarily captures pure difference.

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